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4 1 **On the dose dependence prior and after stimulation with visible light of E'**
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7 2 **and Al-hole centres in sedimentary quartz: correlation and mechanisms**
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25 10 **Abstract**
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27 11 E' and Al-hole centres are some of the most common and abundant paramagnetic defects in
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29 12 sedimentary quartz. Here we investigate the dose dependence of these defects before and after
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31 13 exposure to light by electron spin resonance (ESR). Unlike the Al-hole centre, known to have
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33 14 only radiation-induced formation mechanisms, the E' seems to possess a response to gamma
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35 15 dose characterised by predominantly radiation-induced annihilation at lower doses (about 1000
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37 16 Gy) and a predominantly radiation-induced formation at higher doses, at least in our investigated
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39 17 dose range (up to 40 kGy). We propose these dose response mechanisms to be governed by
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41 18 electron trapping by E' itself and by hole trapping by the oxygen deficiency centre (ODC),
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43 19 known to be the main precursor of E'. We show that the ESR signals of both defects are linearly
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45 20 correlated during their formation as well as during their dissociation under both irradiation and
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47 21 sunlight exposure. We further show that there is a clear correlation between the light sensitive
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49 22 Al-hole centres (also known as the Al-hole bleachable part), and the amount of E' produced after
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51 23 prolonged light exposure. This indicates a correlation between the holes released from Al-hole
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53 24 and those trapped by one of the two electrons in the ODCs producing E'. As such, the origin of
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4 25 the unbleachable part of the Al-hole signal resides in the availability of oxygen deficiency
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6 26 centres which are also dependent on the accumulated gamma dose.

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9 27 **Key words:** electron spin resonance; E' centres; Al-hole centres; gamma dose response;
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11 28 mechanisms; bleaching; correlation.
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15 30 **Highlights**

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18 31 Gamma-irradiation leads to E' dissociation as well as its formation in respect to dose.

19 32 Oxygen deficiency centre (ODC) is the main precursor of E' centre.

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21 33 Al-hole and E' show a strong correlation under electronic excitations.

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23 34 The electron-hole recombination or the bleaching process occurs at Al-hole/ODC site.

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25 35 The Al-unbleached part is related the ODC concentration in quartz.
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32 37 **Introduction**

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35 38 Paramagnetic defects (i.e. containing at least one unpaired electron) in sedimentary quartz are
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37 39 relevant for dating (Toyoda and Ikeya, 1991a; Laurent et al., 1998; Toyoda, 2011). Thus,
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41 40 understanding the physical processes occurring in this mineral under different electronic
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43 41 excitations such as irradiation with ionising radiation or exposure to visible light (the resetting
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45 42 agent in sediment dating also known as bleaching) is of paramount importance. Indeed, both
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47 43 these electronic excitations are known to affect quantitatively defects in quartz. Due to their
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49 44 concentration (Usami et al., 2009; Preusser et al., 2009; Jani et al., 1983), their dose response
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51 45 (Benzid and Timar-Gabor, 2019; Wei et al., 2019) and their thermal stability (Toyoda and Ikeya,
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53 46 1991a) E' ($O\equiv Si^* + Si\equiv O$) and Al-hole ($[AlO_4/h^+]^0$) centres are some of the most important
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55 47 paramagnetic centres in quartz.
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48 Beside the knock-on process (Imai et al., 1988; Tsai and Griscom, 1991; Imai and Hirashima,
49 1994) and the atomic displacement (Shluger, 1988; Shluger and Stefanovich, 1990; Song et al.,
50 2000) known to be part of the formation mechanism of point defects in silica glass and quartz,
51 electrons (e^-) and holes (h^+) are the main species that the ionizing gamma-irradiation produces,
52 hence their role in the production of known paramagnetic centres in quartz is primordial
53 (Griscom, 2011).

54 E' centre consists of an unpaired electron trapped at an oxygen vacancy, while Al-hole centre
55 consists of hole trapped by substitutional trivalent aluminium at a silicon site. Electron spin
56 resonance (ESR) spectroscopy is recognised to be one of the best selective techniques to probe
57 and study these centres individually. Although E' is ubiquitous in quartz the mechanisms of its
58 formation as well as its behaviour under irradiation remain debatable. Rink and Odom (1991)
59 proposed that E' is generated as a part in a Frenkel pair by alpha recoil processes, while Toyoda
60 et al. (2005) argued that this defect is formed by irradiation with beta- and gamma-rays. Thus,
61 the mechanism of its formation in mixed radiation fields is most likely controlled by both
62 processes mentioned and remains not yet fully understood. Moreover, even the response of this
63 centre to gamma-dose is not well documented and understood. Toyoda and Schwarcz (1997)
64 have observed a slight decrease of E' in quartz at low doses. While a self-annealing mechanism
65 under gamma-irradiation via electron trapping has been proposed for amorphous silica (Devine,
1990), this knowledge has not been further applied in the case of quartz, as far as we are aware
of. The investigations on the gamma dose response curves (DRC) of this centre were focused on
the so-called heat-treated E' and it was shown that this signal grows with dose up to a certain
saturation value, depending on the pre-treatment that has been applied to the sample (Toyoda,
2011; Toyoda and Hattori, 2000; Toyoda and Ikeya, 1991a; Toyoda and Schwarcz, 1997; Usami

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71 et al., 2009). In the case of Al-hole centre, its formation under irradiation has been shown to take
72 place when alkali as well hydrogen ions from compensated aluminium complex are being
73 replaced by holes (Halliburton, 1989; Markes and Halliburton, 1979). In the light of this, a model
74 has been proposed recently to describe the gamma-dose response of Al-hole (Benzid and Timar-
75 Gabor, 2019).

76 Possible correlations between the E' centres and Al-hole centres under electronic excitations
77 have been previously proposed or suggested (see e.g. Jani et al., 1983; Usami et al., 2009 or
78 Spooner et al., 2019). It has been observed that migration of cations as a result of irradiation
79 above 200K (Halliburton, 1989; Markes and Halliburton, 1979) correlate with the production of
80 E' in synthetic quartz (Jani et al., 1983). While on heating, it was found that the decay of Al-hole
81 centres correlate with the growth of heat-treated E' centres. This was explained by the migration
82 of holes from Al-hole centres to oxygen deficiency centres (ODCs), thus producing E' centres
83 (Toyoda and Schwarcz, 1997; Toyoda and Hattori, 2000). Furthermore, (Usami et al., 2009)
84 found that the heat-treated E' concentration in quartz is small in samples possessing low amounts
85 of Al-hole centres. This was justified by the fact that despite the availability of ODCs, the hole
86 supply (from Al-h centres) after heating is not sufficient to convert all ODCs to E' centres.

87 On the other hand, exposure of quartz to sunlight has been shown to increase the E'
88 concentration up to certain maximum (Wei et al., 2019) and to decrease Al-hole centres up to
89 certain minimum, although not reducing it to zero (Tissoux et al., 2012). In a recent study Timar-
90 Gabor et al. (2019) have shown that this residual level of Al-hole signals in sedimentary quartz
91 after light exposure depends on the previously accrued dose.

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92 In this paper, we investigate the correlations between Al-hole and E' centres in natural quartz as
93 function of the accumulated gamma-dose prior and after sunlight exposure and propose
94 mechanisms for the dissociation and the formation of E' centres under these excitations.

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96 **Samples and methods**

97 Sedimentary quartz samples, denoted END 1.2, is 63-90 µm quartz extracted from Holocene soil
98 at loess-paleosol sequence in Enders, Nebraska, Great Plains, USA. For further details on the
99 treatment and extraction of the quartz please refer to Tecsa et al., (2019). An equivalent dose of
100 about 8 Gy was obtained for this sample using standard optically stimulated luminescence (OSL)
101 dating methods. Sample denoted EVA 1098 is 125-212 µm quartz from Lake Durthong
102 Australia, with an OSL equivalent doses of about 72 Gy (Fitzsimmons, 2017). We note here that
103 these equivalent doses are the doses accrued by the samples since the sediment was deposited
104 and the grains were last exposed to daylight. Light exposure under controlled laboratory
105 conditions was carried out using an array of TL29D16/09N lamps with similar spectral
106 characteristics to natural sunlight (Petrusic et al., 2012). We have estimated that one hour of
107 exposure to this lamp corresponds to one hour of daylight exposure during summertime.
108 Irradiations were performed at Centre for Nuclear Technologies, Technical University of
109 Denmark (DTU NUTECH) using a calibrated ⁶⁰Co-60 gamma cell, with a dose rate of about 2
110 Gy/s (dose rate to water) at the time of irradiation. Dose rate to quartz was estimated to be 0.941
111 (with an uncertainty of 2.2% of the ratio) of dose rate to water based on Monte Carlo simulation
112 considering the irradiation geometry used.

113 ESR investigations were carried out using an X band Bruker EMX plus spectrometer. All
114 samples had the same volume, and the mass used for ESR measurements was around 190 mg

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with variation of 5%. In order to avoid the ESR signals overlapping, the E' ESR signal was recorded at room temperature with a microwave power of 0.02 mW. The Al-hole has no signal at room temperature because of the hole hopping due to thermal agitation. Hence, the ESR signal of Al-hole could be recorded only at low temperature, herein it was recorded at 90K with 2 mW microwave power. An attempt to record the E' ESR signal at 90K was done but the signal is strongly affected by the Al-hole signal (see Fig. 1), especially for high doses, even at very low microwave power. In order to quantify the variation of defect concentration, we have measured the amplitude pick-to-pick (App) of the ESR signals where the ESR linewidth has been verified to have no significant variation with dose, hence, App variation could be taken as very good approximation of the effective concentration variation (Chesnut, 1977).

Results

Figure 1 exhibits the ESR spectra of END1.2 sample recorded at 90K with 2 mW and at room temperature (RT) with 0.02 mW of microwave power. The App of Al-hole and E' are indicated.

Figure 1: ESR spectrum of END1.2 sample recorded at 90 K, 9417.5 MHz, and 2 mW. Figure inset represents the ESR spectrum of E' recorded at RT, 9404.2 MHz, and 0.02 mW.

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132 Figure 2 presents the evolution of ESR intensities of E' and Al-hole centres as function of
133 accumulated gamma-dose. For doses of less than about 1000 Gy the E' centre intensity shows a
134 significant decrease while the Al-hole centre intensity shows a rapid growth with dose for the
135 END1.2 sample. The same trend can be seen in EVA1098 although the drop in E' is less
136 pronounced than in END1.2. This could be due to the higher initial concentration of E' in
137 END1.2 than in EVA1098 sample. Although the different amplitudes, E' decreases in both
138 samples with almost the same decaying rate (231 Gy^{-1} and 287 Gy^{-1} , respectively), as shown by
139 fitting the data with a decaying exponential. For doses more than 1000 Gy, both the E' and Al-
140 hole centre intensities increase with gamma dose, at least for the dose range investigated herein.
141 As it can be seen from figure 2, the data for E' in this dose range could be fitted by a single
142 saturating exponential function. The saturation characteristic dose for the exponential increase in
143 E' above 1000 Gy is similar for both samples ($1.3 \cdot 10^4 \text{ Gy}^{-1}$ and $1.4 \cdot 10^4 \text{ Gy}^{-1}$, respectively).
144 Remarkably, this value is also consistent with that obtained for the saturation exponential in the
145 sum of two saturating exponential function model used to represent the growth of Al-hole with
146 dose ($2.2 \cdot 10^4 \text{ Gy}^{-1}$ and $1.7 \cdot 10^4 \text{ Gy}^{-1}$, respectively).

Figure 2: Evolution of the ESR intensities of E' and Al-hole centres as function of accumulated gamma dose for END1.2 sample: **a)** E' centres, **b)** Al-hole centres, and for EVA1098: **c)** E' centres, **d)** Al-hole centres.

Figure 3 exhibits the dose dependence of E' and Al-hole in both samples after three consecutive months of sunlight exposure. Timar-Gabor et al., (2019) have shown that after such a prolonged light exposure the residuals of Al-hole signals do no longer decrease with further exposure. One can see that the dose response curves (Fig. 2) were dramatically changed for both paramagnetic defects. The data points of figure 3 have been fitted for E' by the sum of two single saturating exponential functions. For the Al-hole we have fitted the data by a single saturating exponential in consistence with the findings of our recent work (see Timar-Gabor et al., 2019). The dose dependence of E' at low doses ($D < 1\text{kGy}$) is not well described due to lack of data points for sample END1.2, however for EVA1098 sample where more data points are available, one can see that the sum of two single saturating exponential functions describes well the dataset.

Figure 3: The evolution of ESR intensities of E' and Al-hole centres as function of gamma dose after three months of sunlight exposure of END1.2 sample; **a)** E' centres, **b)** Al-hole centres, and of EVA1098 sample; **c)** E' centres, **d)** Al-hole centres.

Figure 4 shows the dependence between the ESR intensities of E' and Al-hole centres with respect to the accumulated gamma dose before and after sunlight exposure. The datasets was fitted by a linear function of the form: $I_{E'} = A + B \times I_{Al-hole}$ where I is the defect ESR intensity (App), A is the intercept, and B is the slope.

Before exposure, the ESR intensity of E' centres versus that of the Al-hole centres show a negative correlation below 1 kGy and a positive correlation above this dose, whereas after exposure, they correlate positively but with different slopes, much higher below 1 kGy than above. Note that in figure 4.b below 1 kGy the slope of the correlation line is not relevant due to the lack of data points for END1.2 sample; however, for EVA1098 sample (Fig. 4.d) in the case

176 of which enough data points are available, one can see that the correlation between the two
 177 defects exists.

178 **Figure 4:** Correlation between the ESR intensities of E' and Al-hole in the respect to the
 179 accumulated gamma dose in END1.2; **a)** before and **b)** after three months of sunlight exposure
 180 and in EVA1098; **c)** before and **d)** after three months of sunlight exposure. The dashed lines
 181 indicate the ESR intensities measured at 1 kGy. The slopes 'B' of the correlation lines are
 182 indicated as well in the figures.

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 185 Figure 5 represents the relative amount of the light-induced E' centres, expressed as a percentage
 186 of the E' centres after exposure, as well as the relative amount of light-annihilated Al-hole
 187 centres, expressed as a percentage of the initial Al-h concentration, as function of accumulated
 188 gamma dose in both samples (Fig.5a and 5.b). One can see that both defects show a similar
 189 tendency in respect to dose. Figure 5.c shows that the variation of the relative amount of light-
 190 induced E' centres as function of that of light-annihilated Al-hole centres in the respect of

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7 192 same, with the correlation slope found to be around unity with a deviation of about 20%.

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194 **Figure 5:** The relative amount of light-annihilated Al-hole centres and light-induced E' centres
195 as function accumulated gamma dose after three months of light exposure of **a)** END 1.2 and **b)**
196 EVA1098, **c)** the correlation between the relative amounts of light-induced E' and light-
197 annihilated Al-hole.

199 Discussion

200 Inducing defects by irradiation is expected to be less effective in synthetic as well as in heat
201 treated natural quartz than in natural sedimentary quartz due to the virtually perfect
202 crystallization of the former than of the latter. As a result, one can expect that the dose
203 dependence, especially for structural defects, such as the E' centre and ODC, to be quantitatively
204 different in the case of natural quartz compared to the case of synthetic and pre-heated quartz.
205 However, the physical mechanisms behind the formation and the dissociation of both structural

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206 and impurity related defects in quartz, synthetic or natural (heated or non-heated), must be
207 qualitatively similar. The irradiation-induced annihilation of E' at low doses (D < 1 kGy) (Fig.
208 2.a and 2.c) has been previously observed in natural quartz (Toyoda and Schwarcz, 1997). Since
209 that study was presented, this phenomenon did not receive significant attention from researchers.
210 As far as studies on amorphous silica are concerned, it was proposed that irradiation-induced
211 diffusing diatomic oxygen could interact with E' leading to its dissociation and the production of
212 peroxy radical (Devine, 1990). But other studies report that the diffusion of diatomic oxygen in
213 irradiated high-purity fused silica could take place for a temperature starting from 400 K
214 (Griscom, 1990). For our samples, we have checked the dose response of the peroxy radicals and
215 no significant change or trend was observed, at least for the dose range studied herein (up to 40
216 kGy), leading us to rule out the occurrence of this process. Consequently, the process behind the
217 dissociation of E' (see Fig.2a and 2.c) is probably an electronic process. The decrease of the ESR
218 intensity of E', seen below 1 kGy, could be explained by the self-annealing mechanism proposed
219 by Devine (1990) for amorphous silica, where E' is transformed via trapping an ionizing electron
220 and forming the oxygen deficiency centre (ODC) as:

222 We propose that the mechanism leading to E' formation is holes recombining with one of the
223 two electrons of ODC leaving the second one trapped at the oxygen vacancy as:

225 This second mechanism was proposed and investigated widely in synthetic and natural quartz
226 reporting ODCs to be the main precursors of E' centres (Toyoda and Schwarcz, 1997; Toyoda
227 and Hattori, 2000; Moritani et al., 2005; Imai and Hirashima, 1994; Imai et al., 1988).

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228 Under gamma irradiation, it is judicious to assume that both mechanisms (1), namely electron
229 trapping by E', as well as (2), namely hole trapping by ODC, take place simultaneously. The rate
230 should depend on the precursors concentration in each mechanism, as well as on the e⁻ and h⁺
231 supplies. It is worthwhile to note that the mobility of these carriers is playing also an important
232 role. This is generally higher for e⁻ than for h⁺. In our case the rate of mechanism (1) was found
233 to be about 50 times higher than that of mechanism (2). We note that the rate expressed here is
234 the inverse of the saturation dose characteristic of the exponential process. By fitting the data in
235 figure 2, we obtained ~1/250 Gy⁻¹ for mechanism (1) and ~1/1.3 10⁴ Gy⁻¹ for mechanism (2),
236 respectively. The reason why mechanism (1) quenches for a dose of about 1000 Gy is not clear
237 yet, but it could originate from the decay in the electron supply or to the fact that some E' centres
238 are beyond the reach of mobile electrons. Further studies are needed to securely ascertain the
239 mechanism behind.

240 The production of the Al-hole centres ([AlO₄/h⁺]⁰) has been discussed in our recent study
241 (Benzid and Timar-Gabor, 2019) in which we have shown that the formation of this centre as
242 function of gamma dose could take place through two main mechanisms and an intermediate
243 reaction between them:

246 where M⁺ is a monovalent cation (Li⁺, Na⁺...etc.) and H⁺ refers to the hydrogen ion.

247 The production of Al-hole centres with gamma dose has been reported to follow the sum of two
248 single saturating exponential functions; each of them corresponding mainly to one of the
249 sequences 3a and 3b, respectively (Benzid and Timar-Gabor, 2019).

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250 Exposing the samples to sunlight for a long duration (three months) affects dramatically the dose
251 response curve of both centres (Fig. 3). The results here for the Al-hole centre are in line with
252 our previous findings, namely that the signal is reduced after light exposure, with the value to
253 which the signal has decreased depending exponentially on the previously given dose (Timar et
254 al., 2019). The increase of E' centre after exposure to light is not understood physically yet,
255 although a similar behaviour was recently reported and even proposed for tracing the natural
256 sediment provenance (Wei et al., 2019). The formation of E' after light exposure occurs probably
257 via mechanism (2), namely through hole trapping by ODC. By considering mechanisms (1) and
258 (2) one should note however that the ODC concentration should be also dose dependent. Indeed,
259 the hole population also plays an equally important role, as shown by the mechanism (2). Here
260 we show that this hole population (released) corresponds to the Al-hole centres concentration
261 that was annihilated by visible light exposure. The dose response of E' after light exposure is
262 found to follow the sum of two single exponential functions (Fig. 3.a and 3.c). This may be due
263 to the dose dependence of the ODC concentration, that is probably increasing below 1 kGy
264 according to the mechanism (1), and then decreasing above 1 kGy according to the mechanism
265 (2), a dose region where a part of ODCs have been converted by irradiation to E' (Fig. 2.a and
266 2.c). Comparing the increase with dose of the Al-hole residual signal (fitted by an single
267 saturating exponential function on the whole dose range) to the increase of E' after light
268 exposure, one can see that the dose saturation characteristic of Al-hole residual is similar to the
269 that of the later saturating exponential used to fit the E' signal intensity after exposure (about 20
270 to 30 kGy (Fig. 3)). This is further indication that the process behind the production of E' and the
271 process behind the dissociation of Al-hole by light exposure are related to each other.

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272 According to mechanisms (1), (2), and (3), during the irradiation process and before light
273 exposure, the correlation line represents the variation of E' concentration as function of that of
274 Al-hole where the slope is the proportionality constant between the two defects in respect of
275 dose. This could also be interpreted in the following manner. Below 1 kGy the slope (Fig. 4)
276 should correlate also to the ratio of the number of electrons that have been trapped by E'
277 producing ODC via mechanism (1), to the number of holes interacting with diamagnetic
278 compensated Al-centres ($[AlO_4/H^+]^0$ and $[AlO_4/M^+]^0$) producing Al-hole centres via mechanisms
279 (3). Whereas above 1kGy, the slope should correlate to the ratio of the number of holes
280 interacting with ODC producing E' through the mechanisms (2) and the number of holes
281 involved in the mechanisms (3) producing Al-hole centre.

282 Halliburton (1989) has reported that when irradiation-induced electron and hole recombined
283 occurs at $[AlO_4/H^+]^0$ centres, the energy released during this process may free the proton.
284 Presuming that the energy of the recombination is the same of that of disintegration, one can
285 postulate the following scenario: if disintegration of electron-hole pairs, probably in the form of
286 self-trapped excitons, occurs at $[AlO_4/H^+]^0$ and the energy released frees the proton, the hole
287 would be trapped by compensated Al-centre producing Al-hole, and the electron would be
288 trapped by E' producing ODC. Hence, the formation of Al-hole and the dissociation E' should
289 take place with similar rate below 1 kGy (see Fig. 2).

290 Above 1 kGy, both paramagnetic defects are produced via interaction with holes, showing
291 almost similar production rates (see Fig. 2). The slopes of the correlation lines are less than unity
292 (~0.1 to 0.2) (see figure 4). This can be attributed to the different initial concentration of the
293 precursors in our samples.

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294 After light exposure, both paramagnetic defects correlate with each other (Fig. 4.b and 4.d). We
295 interpret this in terms of holes being transferred from light sensitive Al-hole centres to ODCs.
296 The slopes of the linear dependencies were found to be much greater below 1 kGy than above.
297 We attribute this as due to ODC concentration that is dose dependent according to the
298 mechanisms (1 and 2) (see above). When the relative amount of the light-induced E' and that of
299 the light-annihilated Al-hole centres in both samples in the respect of accumulated gamma dose
300 (Fig. 5.a & 5.b) are plotted, the strong correlation between the growth of E' and the annihilation
301 of Al-hole centres under visible light exposure with a slope around unity and an deviation of
302 about 20% (see Fig. 5.c) indicates that the hole population released from Al-hole centres is of the
303 order of magnitude of hole population behind the production of E' centres.
304 The recombination between electron and holes under thermal electronic excitation has been
305 previously assumed to occur between E' and Al-hole centres. Toyoda and Ikeya, (1991b and
306 1991a) explained the observed increase of E' and decrease of Al-hole by the recombination of
307 one of the two electrons of ODC with a hole released from Al-hole centre, a hypothesis in an
308 accordance to the work of Jani et al., (1983). Under optical electronic excitation, the Al-hole
309 centre was proposed as an electron-hole recombination centre in pair with a neighbouring defect
310 that so far remains unknown (Itoh et al., 2002; Williams and Spooner, 2018). We provide an
311 alternative explanation; the energy band-gap in quartz is known to be about 9 eV (e.g.
312 Halliburton, 1989; Gudmundsdóttir et al., 2015). The Al-hole state is found to be around 2.2 eV
313 above the valence band edge (Gudmundsdóttir et al., 2015). The ODC was found to possess two
314 energetic levels, due to the relaxation of silicon atoms toward each other when an oxygen atom is
315 missing, one doubly occupied at lower state (the bonding state) and other one empty at higher
316 state (the antibonding state), with the empty state close to the conduction band edge and the

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317 doubly occupied state about 6.7 eV below the conduction band edge (Rudra and Fowler, 1987).
318 Accordingly, if the calculated energy states are accurate, any electronic excitation of about one
319 tenth eV more or less is able to promote the recombination between ODC electrons with Al-hole
320 holes.

321
322 Conclusion

323
324 We investigated the responses of E' and Al-hole defects in sedimentary quartz to gamma
325 irradiation as well as to light exposure after the material was irradiated. Al-hole signal
326 dependence with dose can be described by a sum of two exponential functions and a
327 phenomenological model for this behaviour was recently presented by Benzid and Timar-Gabor
328 (2019). The value of the Al-hole signal remaining after prolonged exposure to sunlight was
329 shown to depend exponentially on the previous given dose (Timar-Gabor et al., 2019).

330 Here we show that E' decreases exponentially under irradiation up to doses of about 1000 Gy,
331 followed by an increase for larger doses. This was explained by two mechanisms, irradiation-
332 induced annihilation due to electron trapping by E' itself and irradiation-induced formation due
333 to hole trapping by its precursor, the oxygen deficiency centre (ODC). We have shown that Al-
334 hole and E' show a strong linear correlation in the course of their formation and/or their
335 dissociation as well prior and after artificial sunlight exposure in the respect of the previous
336 accumulated dose. After exposing our samples to sunlight, the relative amount of the light-
337 induced E' centres, as well as the relative amount of light-annihilated Al-hole centres were
338 linearly correlated with a slope of unity indicating a strong correlation between the hole
339 population removed from Al-hole centres and the hole population interacting with ODCs

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340 producing E' centres thereby. This suggests that during the bleaching process, the oxygen
341 deficient centres are converted into E' centres by electron-hole recombination that occurs at
342 ODC/Al-hole sites. Exhausting the ODCs is equivalent to exhausting the electron population that
343 is energetically favoured to recombine the holes at Al-hole sites. The ODC concentration is
344 sample-dependent as well as dose-dependent. Consequently, when dating applications using Al-
345 hole electron spin resonance signals are performed one should expect that the so-called
346 unbleachable part of Al-hole signal (also known as the residual) to be sample and dose
347 dependent.

348
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362 formation in sedimentary quartz upon room temperature irradiation: electron spin

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